

Exploring the Impact of Artificial Intelligence as a Guide for Students during Assessment

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Abstract

This Artificial intelligence (AI) is a rapidly growing field of technology that has the potential to transform every aspect of our social interactions. In education, AI is beginning to generate new teaching and learning solutions, which are currently being tested in a variety of contexts. And if we apply AI in student assessments as a guide for them to understand more effectively the exam format and instructions, we can use the custom GPT. This article highlights the impact of critical integration of AI into learner assessment and focuses on the role of AI as a companion to assessment. By exploring the possibilities offered by customised GPT, we aim to demonstrate the impact and the potential of AI to transform the assessment experience for students. In this paper, we discuss the implementation of this method, its impacts on the learner, and provide recommendations to improve limitations for better future results. Our study results indicate that AI-assisted assessments significantly enhance students' understanding of exam formats and instructions, leading to improved academic performance. Survey data also shows a positive perception among students, with most finding AI assistance more beneficial than traditional methods. However, some challenges were identified, highlighting areas for further improvement. This study serves as a step towards achieving more effective integration of AI in learner assessments.

Keywords: Project Approaches; Learner's Evaluation; Artificial Intelligence; GPT; Custom GPT; Assessment experience.

1 Introduction

In recent decades, Artificial intelligence (AI) has undergone a huge evolution in many different fields such as medicine, manufacturing, transportation and education. In fact, AI is only a 60-year-old discipline that brings together science, theory, and technology particularly mathematical logic, statistics, probability, computational neurobiology, and computer science, and its purpose is about making machines perform cognitive functions to imitate humans (Sokolov and A 2019).

AI aims to enable machines to perform tasks using knowledge representations, reasoning modelling, text analysis and data extraction, and many other method (Zhang et al. 2021). It stands as a beacon of innovation, reshaping the way we approach learning and career development. In fact, the effective integration of AI skills into education requires a pedagogical framework.

Furthermore, while AI continues to advance at a staggering pace, the realisation of fully autonomous technologies, such as driverless vehicles, remains a distant prospect, highlighting the complex journey ahead.

The implementation of AI in education offers capabilities and potential to overcome many major challenges. It's bringing about a paradigm shift in education by providing revolutionary solutions to persistent problems and improving the quality of education.

Nowadays, emerging AI technologies have already been shown to have a positive impact on education, increasing learner engagement and motivation. The educational landscape is evolving profoundly, with innovation and adaptation driving the use of AI-powered solutions by both instructors and students. That's why they are massively using AI tools to support the learning and teaching process (Huang, Saleh, and Liu 2021).

Indeed, after the introduction of ChatGPT, from November 2021 to the present, we have seen an evolution in which the use of this ChatGPT increases, especially in learning (Montenegro-Rueda et al. 2023). This evolution demonstrates the growing reliance on ChatGPT as a valuable tool for knowledge acquisition and personal development. What's more, its integration with a variety of platforms and applications promotes its widespread adoption, making it more accessible and advantageous for users seeking knowledge and assistance.

Nevertheless, as our dependence on AI for learning support grows, questions about its application to learner assessment are raised (Hargreaves 2023). In fact, assessment in education plays a very important role in informing the various stakeholders about student progress, providing guidance for educational decisions, measuring effectiveness and encouraging student performance by validating learning achievements (Doğan et al. 1AD).

Indeed, students often find themselves in situations where they are assessed on one or more specific criteria as part of well-defined examinations. This pressure they feel during assessments can lead to considerable levels of stress. The latter varies according to the context of school assessments. Studies have shown that stress during examinations can lead to reduced performance and increased emotional tension (Tokaeva, Parshina, and Pavlenkovich 2012). This will affect the students' performance and put them in a situation where they won't fully understand the exam statement.

However, it's undeniable that the use of AI in exams does not benefit learners and can potentially harm their educational experience. Using AI tools during exams can increase the risks of cheating or breaching academic ethics. Students could use AI methods to access unapproved information, collaborate with their classmates, or manipulate evaluation results. AI algorithms can perpetuate existing prejudices and stereotypes, leading to unfair and inaccurate assessments of student performance (Panagopoulou, Parpoula, and Karpouzis 2023). Because of this, it is crucial to guarantee impartiality and justice in learner assessments, which necessitates a thorough analysis of the ethical issues related to the use of AI in educational assessment and, learner assessment should always be objective and open to everyone. As AI continues to advance in education, maintaining fairness and openness in student assessment remains an important consideration.

Considering that, the main objective of this article is how to integrate IA in learners' assessment exploring their role as a guide during examinations and to investigate its impact on students.

This integration was implemented in a continuous assessment test within a module called "Web Technology Project," dedicated to second-year students at ESPRIT, aiming to evaluate their ongoing progress effectively.

In this context, this paper examines the following research inquiry, how can AI be an effective tool for personalising academic advising? And how does this personalised approach underscore the importance of using AI in academic exams?

2 Description of the module

The course "Web Technology Project " is an important six-credit module of the curriculum for second-year students common core IT students at ESPRIT School of engineering. The primary goal of this enlightening module is to provide students with the necessary skills to conceive, develop and execute a web-based technology project using HTML, PHP, and JavaScript languages. At the end of the course, students will have the capability to create a project in a group, elaborate on it, and recognize associated requirements. Additionally, they will have the capacity to collaborate efficiently in order to finish the project according to the timeline.

Evaluation of this module depends on two types of grades: assessments throughout the course and the project itself. The final grade is calculated by combining these two factors, with 30% for continuous assessment and 70% for the project evaluation.

This assessment method pays attention to students' comprehension of module concepts and their capacity to apply their knowledge.

3 Proposed Method

Assessments, which aim to measure students' skills and understanding, are crucial but can be hampered by problems such as unclear questions, complex situations and complex language. After the assessment of learning outcomes, we sometimes find that the majority of examinations that fail to produce good results are due to poorly posed questions, confusing problem scenarios or case studies using vocabulary that is difficult for some learners to understand. Unclear questions limit the ability to communicate understanding, while complicated subject areas such as mathematics or law make it difficult to put acquired ideas into practice. What's more, complex language poses a challenge, especially for students from diverse linguistic backgrounds. These obstacles act like linguistic landmines, unfairly disadvantaging some and obscuring the genuine learning achievements waiting to be revealed.

To ensure exams truly fulfil their purpose, students will need an assistant who can clarify the content of an exam without, of course, answering the question. As the teacher cannot be present on the day of the exam, it is important to put in place a system that enables students to benefit from guidance and support. So, students can get the help and support they need to assimilate the exam content without compromising the integrity of the assessment procedure. It enables students to manage their own learning process by providing them with the resources they need to succeed.

The use of an intelligent assistant (AI) is a solution as AI can provide students with personalised assistance. It can answer their questions in order to guide them in their thinking. Using an AI assistant for personalised assessment assistance can improve the learning experience by encouraging critical thinking, guided problem solving, and enhancing accessibility and inclusivity. By using AI, students are encouraged to analyse critically during assessments, examining the reasons behind their answers rather than simply repeating information. This encourages a better understanding of the topic and reinforces important analytical skills. In addition, Artificial Intelligence offers individualised guidance and recommendations to students when faced with complex assessments, acting as a valuable mentor. By helping students with complex problems and offering personalised support, AI helps them develop effective problem-solving strategies. What's more, AI encourages integration into the educational environment by offering assessment assistance to all students, whatever their requirements or position, ensuring the same opportunity for success for all learners. Fundamentally, incorporating these principles into the use of AI for assessment support improves academic performance and promotes the development of essential skills for lifelong learning and success. Moreover, AI can be used to ensure exam fairness. It can ensure that all students have access to the same information and support.

A promising pedagogical innovation is the use of intelligent assistance in the form of personalised chats on the GPT model during exams. This assistant can organise exam descriptions in the form of a knowledge database so that students can ask specific questions relating solely to the content of the exam. The assistant will not say that he or she will answer the questions on the exams, but will be an explanatory guide on how to answer the questions, explain the problem situations, etc... The AI assistant serves as a mentor to assist students in grasping concepts and finding solutions by offering guidance rather than direct answers. Providing immediate feedback enhances learning by enabling the instructor to correct students' misconceptions and

steer them in the correct direction. Adaptive learning systems provide personalised assistance, as efforts to promote accessibility and inclusivity aim to enhance educational access (Wang et al. 2023). Considering ethical principles is crucial, especially in upholding the integrity and confidentiality of exams. Teachers can establish a learning atmosphere that promotes in-depth comprehension, analytical thinking, and inclusive teaching methods through the use of intelligent support.

Teachers play an important role in the initial configuration of the wizard called Custom ChatGPT, defining parameters and limits and providing clear guidelines for its use. Advanced settings can include defining a limited number of questions that students are allowed to ask to encourage effective use of the assistant, as well as establishing guidelines for appropriate use. To ensure academic integrity, assistants may also be strictly forbidden from directly answering students' questions or accessing information on the Internet. The advantages of such intelligent assistance are manifold. It must be designed to be accessible to all levels of understanding and use simple, clear language. In addition, the interactive design of the assistant allows students to ask questions in real time, facilitating a dynamic learning environment. This encourages students' active participation in the consulting process and reinforces their understanding of key concepts. Finally, you can maximise its usefulness by customising your assistant to take account of your students' individual needs and preferences.

By adapting the explanations given to students to their specific level of understanding, assistants can play an important role in providing differentiated support to meet the diverse needs of the student population. And with the functionality of a custom version of ChatGPT that allows users to combine instructions, knowledge, and skills to customise it for specific tasks and topics, we can create an Exam Guide that can be the AI assistant for the student. The role of a custom GPT is to enable the creation of specialised, fine-tuned versions of the base GPT model. While creating it, you are asked to make some configuration and put restrictions for the student.

Below is an organigram outlining the method described:

Figure 1. AI Assessment Guide Method

After creating the custom GPT we distribute it to the students for use during the web technologies project module test session. Students are permitted to utilise it throughout the duration of the exam.

4 Results

In previous sections, we have detailed the technique employed in our research, outlining the chosen approach in detail. By exploring in depth, we ensure an instructive journey through the results generated by this approach when put into practice.

Our investigation draws from two distinct yet interrelated streams of evidence: scholarly research and survey responses. By combining existing academic discourse and collecting first-hand data, our aim is to provide a balanced view of the effectiveness and implications of the guided exam custom ChatGPT.

4.1 Scholar Results

In Tunisia, learners are evaluated with scores ranging from 0 to 20. We utilized the proposed approach with 30 students to calculate the Continuous Assessment grade, which accounts for 30% of the overall average.

We compared scholar results using continuous monitoring grades from both the traditional and AI assistant approaches.

Continuous Assessment Grades

Figure 2. Histogram chart for Continuous Assessment grades

The histogram illustrates the distribution of student scores ranging from 0 to 20. Every bar shows the frequency of scores within specific intervals. When we compared the grades of continuous monitoring using traditional methods and AI assistant methods, we noticed a significant discrepancy. Using the suggested method led to a significant enhancement in academic performance, evident from a move towards better grades. This enhancement indicates that students could boost their grades by utilizing the suggested approach.

4.2 Survey Results

The survey included 5 questions about this experience (experiment). Questions with responses are listed here in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of Student Feedback on AI Integration in Assessments,

Question	Totally Disagree	Disagree	No opinion	Agree	Fully Agree
The AI-assisted assessment experience was more beneficial than traditional assessment methods.	0%	3,33 %	13,33%	26,67%	56,67%
The use of AI in assessments significantly enhanced my understanding of the exam format and instructions.	1%	2,33 %	10,33%	38,45%	47,89%
I encountered challenges or limitations while using the custom GPT for assessments.	3,3%	16,7%	50%	20%	10%
Integrating AI into learner assessments should be further improved based on my experience.	6,02%	16,7%	30%	21,50%	25,78%
I believe AI-assisted assessments should be integrated into more educational contexts to enhance the learning experience.	1%	3,33 %	20,33%	30%	45,34%

According to Table 1, we found out that the results of the survey show that the respondents have a mostly favourable view of AI-assisted assessments. Most people believe that AI helps improve the assessment process more than traditional methods do, with almost half saying that AI greatly improves their comprehension of exam formats and instructions. Nevertheless, a significant number faced difficulties or constraints when utilizing the tailored GPT for evaluations, indicating areas that could be enhanced. Participants showed a keen interest in improving and incorporating AI into student evaluations, acknowledging its ability to improve the learning process.

Overall, the results suggest a positive perception of AI-assisted assessments, with acknowledgment of both benefits and challenges. There is a clear indication of a desire for further improvement and integration of AI in educational settings.

For this reason, we decided to use the survey data to optimize our approach to integrating AI-assisted assessments in education. The findings highlight the need to overcome challenges, increase user satisfaction and preparing students for the future workforce emerged as key priorities. By embracing feedback, fostering innovation, and prioritizing ethical practices, educators can optimize AI's transformative impact on learning experiences.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented our personalised method using custom ChatGPT as a guide in student assessments. The aim was to see whether this method can effectively replace actual teacher assistance during the exam, to enhance learning and provide useful information for students.

Research findings indicated that the use of personalized ChatGPT during assessments led to positive results. Students described a more beneficial assessment experience than conventional approaches, with significant advances in understanding of different exam types and instructions. In addition, the individualized assistance provided by the custom Chat contributed to a better assimilation of subjects and boosted overall academic performance.

Despite the promise of results, we are aware of the need for continued progress. Some modifications are required to improve the overall experience. This involves improving artificial intelligence algorithms to solve problems, improving user interfaces for an enhanced user experience and prioritizing ethical considerations when evaluating.

In conclusion, our study demonstrates the potential of guided exams as a valuable tool for assessing students, providing insight into its effectiveness and areas for improvement. By taking into account feedback and making modifications, we can apply this method in projects at ESPRIT as well, creating specific AI assistant for each module to further enhance the learning experience.

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